

DEVELOPMENT OF PERFORMANCE SKILLS OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TRADITIONAL SINGING)

Karshibayev is the son of Zahidjon Uralboy

ORCHID:0009-0009-2739-0508

Email:zokhidjon_karshibaev@mail.ru

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi

1st stage foundation doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385225>

ABSTRACT:

The article examines the development of performance skills in traditional singing through an integrative approach. In the article, an integrated approach to the development of performance skills includes the complex interaction of various aspects of music education, including musical thinking, emotional performance, creative expression, and the use of modern technologies. they offer. The article also examines examples of practical exercises and methods that help students develop their performance skills in traditional singing.

Keywords: traditional singing, technical skills, expressiveness, singing, performance skills, practical training, individual approach.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbek national traditional singing is one of the most ancient and unique types of art, and it is one of the main factors that conveys and preserves the cultural and historical values of the nation. The issue of preserving and conveying the unique cultural heritage of the people, studying traditional singing, does not lose its relevance in any time and place. Traditional singing is an integral part of Uzbek culture and reflects the history and mentality of the people, customs and traditions. In addition, the study of traditional singing contributes to the development of the science and art of music, and also promotes cultural exchange and interaction between different peoples. As part of our research, we will consider the development of performance skills in traditional singing through an integrative approach.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS FROM TOPIC SURFACE

The integrated approach in performing arts is a format that meets the needs of the modern world, that is, the essence of the approach is focused on the practical application of knowledge, which helps to solve problems related to one subject using the tools of another.

In modern psychological and pedagogical sciences, there are a number of studies devoted to the characteristics and laws of personal development of students.

The works of NA Alekseev, DA Belukhina, EV Bondarevskaya, VV Serikov, IS Yakimanskaya adequately cover the philosophical and psychological-pedagogical aspects of the person-oriented approach to education. The works of scientists in the field of integration in didactic education were of particular importance for our research (MA Danilov, I. Ya. Lerner, MN Skatkin); humanization of education (RA Valeeva, GV Mukhametzyanova, ZG Nigmatov, etc.); CT Shatsky, AS Makarenko, VN Soroki-Rosinsky, Sh. A. Amonashvili); study of the works of scientists who developed person-oriented, especially interactive, educational technologies (VP Bsepalko, VG Gulchevskaya, GI Ibragimov, MV Klarin, GK Selevko, VT Fomenko, IS Yakimanskaya) was developed.

Perception of music allows students to master various means of speech communication, solve problems related to expressing their thoughts and experiences. It is primarily the delivery of emotional and semantic content resulting from the perception of a musical work that puts children in the real context of complex human emotions and relationships.

The problems of socio-cultural interaction in the information society today are related to all directions of the development of the human personality - his worldview [4, 5], emotional sphere, behavior. Local and foreign researchers wrote about the importance of art, including music, in personality development (LS Vygotsky, EV Nazaykinsky, PM Jacobson, BM Teplov, AA Leontiev, NA Vetlugina, DB Kabalevsky, LV Shkolyar, R. Arnheim, AN Sohor, OV Sokolov, AA Evdokimova, EA Sivukhina, RI udalo-va, SA Fadeeva and others) [1; 3; 6.]. The rules put forward by these authors influenced changes in the modern educational process, taking into account the ideas of humanistic psychology and implementing a person-oriented approach. At the same time, students' aesthetic and general cultural development is based on developing educational principles, relationships between emotional and rational forms of knowing the world.

The musical culture of society, according to a number of researchers, is the unity of music and its social activity [4; 8; 9]. DB Kabalevsky connected the musical culture of the child's personality with the spiritual concept of musical art: the ability to perceive music as a living figurative art born from life and inextricably linked with life, a special "musical feeling" that allows to perceive it emotionally; is the ability to identify the nature of music and feel the inner connection between the nature of music and the nature of its performance.

Perception of music and musical creativity (in the broadest sense of the word), including creation, performance, reproduction, distribution of musical works. According to the well-known psychologist BM Teplov, full artistic perception of

art is an active activity aimed at expanding and deepening knowledge about the world. Undoubted participants in the development of musical culture are all subjects of educational relations (teachers, students, parents), each of them has their own knowledge, skills, abilities and personal characteristics.

The art of listening, the art of feeling, the art of thinking, the art of expressing one's thoughts, and the art of speech are a set of abilities of a child. Therefore, pedagogical support plays an important role in the process of music perception and related creative activity[4;5]. At the same time, it is necessary to create conditions for the development of musical sensitivity, sufficiently perceive the musical image, and express your emotional impressions in figurative speech. ability is important. In our opinion, it is necessary to pay attention to the most effective metasubject and individually planned educational results, including musical results, in the development of musical culture of various participants of educational relations.

DISCUSSION

According to researchers and practitioners, the integrated approach is recognized as an effective way to develop students' musical culture and reveal their creative potential. By integration, in contrast to interdisciplinary relations, we understand not only the interdependence of content, but also the interdependence of visual and expressive tools that can be used in the process of perception, performance and creation of works, taking into account their characteristics.

We associate traditional singing with various art forms, including students creating their own speech statements based on musical impressions. It can be records of different size and genre [2;7].

A prerequisite for such an integrated approach is a system of preparatory exercises, among which several groups can be distinguished: exercises aimed at meaningful perception of musical and literary works; tasks related to enrichment of emotional and musical vocabulary; exercises involving the creation of phrases and sentences related to the perception of music; produce your own speech.

Thus, listening to music can be accompanied by choosing from a synonymous line of words that match the character of the work.

In traditional singing, a piece of music can also serve as a basis for facilitated discussion when its perception is accompanied by a discussion process based on hierarchically structured issues [1].

In the process of listening and performing traditional and instrumental works with a content suitable for students, the use of various drama-izations ("live pictures", drama-ization, one-actor theater, etc.) creates conditions for deeper penetration into the content of the work, its ideas, and its helps to understand the artistic significance.

The interrelationship of artistic images created using different art forms occurs, for example, in the process of artistic illustration, when students use painting to express their impressions of sketches of musical works, operas, ballets, costumes for musical performances, and scenes that cause an emotional response.

Thus, it can be useful to work with the semantic field of the work. When comparing musical and literary works, special attention is paid to highlighting semantic fields and ways of expressing them using different types of art.

To do such work, you can use VG Rajnikov's "dictionary of aesthetic feelings", which allows students not only to expand their vocabulary, but also to verbally understand their emotional states, aesthetic experiences associated with the perception and performance of musical works.

An integrated approach, which allows to connect figurative means of expression, allows to solve the problem of children's understanding of the content of music and speech development of various art forms.

The presence of music as an aesthetic value creates conditions for the emotional and moral formation of children, allows them to acquire moral directions, experience of creative activity.

Thus, the development of musical culture includes a huge pedagogical potential for developing students' creativity, their communicative and speech skills, gaining experience in value areas, and for teachers, accompanying the process of personality development of children. An integrated approach to the development of musical performance skills includes the use of various teaching methods that help musicians expand their knowledge and skills in various areas of musical activity. For example, it can be a combination of individual lessons, master classes, ensemble work, analysis of works, improvisation, as well as the use of modern technologies in music education.

An integrated approach to education is a format that meets the needs of the modern world. It is aimed at the practical application of knowledge and helps to solve problems related to one subject using the tools of another.

An integrated approach to the development of performance skills of students in traditional singing involves the use of various methods to achieve educational

goals. In this case, an integrated approach may include the following aspects: 1. Technical skills: Students can learn breathing, articulation, intonation and other technical aspects of singing, which will help improve the quality of their performance and achieve more expressiveness. 2. Musical understanding: Students can learn about music theory, song structure, and the history of traditional singing genres, which will help them better understand the content and content of the pieces they perform and engage more deeply in the process of making music. 3. Emotional Expressiveness: Students can work on developing emotional sensitivity and expressiveness through singing, which will help them create more vivid and profound interpretations of musical works. 4. individual approach: it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of each student and adapt the teaching method to their needs and capabilities. Different teaching methods and approaches help each student to realize their potential and develop performance skills. Therefore, an integrated approach to the development of performance skills of students in traditional singing includes a comprehensive approach that combines technical skills, musical understanding, emotional expressiveness and an individual approach to each student. Such an approach helps students to become more competent performers and to reveal their creative potential in music.

Table 1. The main aspects of the integrated approach

1. Personalization of training	Every musician is unique, so it's important to consider their individual needs, goals, and playing style when developing a curriculum. This includes creating personalized lesson plans, selecting repertoire that matches student interests, and individualizing teaching methods.
2. Musical thinking	An integrated approach helps students develop their musical thinking by understanding the structure of musical pieces, analyzing musical ideas, and creating their own musical concepts. It helps musicians to express their emotions through music and makes their performances more deep and expressive.
3. Technical skills	An integrated approach involves working on the technique of the instrument to improve coordination, rhythm, articulation and other aspects of technical performance. This allows

	musicians to play complex pieces with ease and confidence.
4. Emotional processing	One of the main aspects of the integrative approach is the development of emotional expressiveness in performance. Musicians learn to convey their emotions and feelings through music, making their performance more intimate.
5. Use of modern technologies	As part of an integrated approach, modern technologies such as music recording and arrangement software, online resources for learning and practice, as well as video lessons and online workshops are used. It allows musicians to expand their knowledge and skills, as well as to use new creative opportunities.

An integrated approach to the development of musical performance skills helps musicians develop in all aspects, helps them become more competent and expressive performers who can communicate through music, inspire others with their creativity.

CONCLUSION

An integral approach to the development of musical performance skills is a comprehensive approach that includes individualization of the educational process, development of musical thinking, technical skills, emotional performance, and the use of modern technologies. This approach contributes to the comprehensive development of musicians, helps them achieve high skill and expressiveness in musical performance. It should be noted that the integrated approach creates conditions for students' creative growth and self-expression, making them more competent and inspiring musicians.

References:

1. Grinberg IG Compositions based on the perception of musical works // Education of Nizhny Novgorod. 2009. No. 2. Pages 163-168.
2. Evdokimova AA Psychology of music perception. N. Novgorod: Nizhny Novgorod Conservatory Publishing House, 2012. 36 seconds
3. Zheleznova T. Ya. Pedagogical outlook as a basis for the formation of professional competence of the future teacher / / Nizhny Novgorod education. 2013. No. 2. Pages 4-11.

4. Zheleznova T. Ya. Improving the professional training of a musician-teacher in the conditions of professional development / / music education and science. 2017. No. 1 (6). Pages 18-22.
5. Sivukhina EA Psychological and pedagogical aspects of education of artistic taste / / historical, philosophical, political and legal sciences, cultural studies and art studies. Theory and practical issues. 2014. No. 8 (46). IS Sections 149-151.

